

PLASTIC SURGERY - TYPES OF OPERATIONS, ADVANTAGES AND DISADVANTAGES, HISTORY

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Abstract: Plastic surgery is a branch of surgery that deals with operative interventions aimed at eliminating deformations and defects of human organs, tissues or body surface.

Key words: plastic surgery, injection, botox, organs, lip

The following plastic operations are often performed: nose, chin and ear correction, forehead and neck skin tightening, blepharoplasty, eyebrow plastic, lip correction, botox injection, liposuction in the abdomen and waist area, bruising reduction and correction of cracks, rejuvenation of hands; In the field of "Galife" liposuction, buttock enlargement, changing the shape of the labia minora and labia majora.

The foundations of modern plastic surgery began at the beginning of the 19th century, when surgeons developed more advanced tools and methods for changing the appearance of a person (the appearance and spread of antiseptics made it possible to transplant skin, tendons and other tissues) was placed.

By the mid-1920s, after the First World War, there were many wounded people in Europe who did not want to accept their shortcomings and asked surgeons not only to restore the function of this or that damaged part of the body, but also asked to improve his appearance. Plastic surgeons have pioneered hundreds of innovative techniques in tissue transplantation, microvessels, maxillofacial surgery, and lipectomy. One of the discoverers and founders of plastic and reconstructive surgery is the famous Armenian-American surgeon Varazdat Gazandyan.

In the 1950s, after the Second World War, further improvements in skin grafting techniques and the quality of new anesthesia (the ability to perform operations under local anesthesia) made plastic surgery safer and therefore more widespread.

TYPES OF PLASTIC SURGERY

Plastic Surgery is divided into two main types - reconstructive and aesthetic.

Reconstructive plastic surgery helps to eliminate deformations, tissue and organ defects and restore their functions by plastic surgery methods. Such operations are performed on persons who have suffered physical injuries due to injury, illness, or have congenital defects. Successful reconstructive surgery can radically change a person's quality of life, help restore his sense of fullness of life, and also help hide obvious genetic defects from a potential spouse.

Aesthetic plastic surgery is the use of plastic surgery methods to improve appearance. Such practices not only prolong people's youth and help them feel their own beauty, but also relieve the emotional stress caused by the perception of real or imagined imperfections, and at the same time significantly improve the quality of life.

Aesthetic plastic surgery can be classified according to the field of operation:

Facial rejuvenation (rhytidectomy, facelift);

Tightening of the eyebrow and forehead (frontlifting);

Plastic eyelids (blepharoplasty);

Nose plastic surgery (rhinoplasty, septoplasty);

Ear plastic (otoplasty);

Lip plastic (cheiloplasty);

Hair transplantation;

Chin plastic (mentoplasty, mandibuloplasty or genioplasty);

Cheek plastic (malarplasty);

Plastic surgery of the neck and chin area (cervicoplasty);

Breast plastic (mammoplasty);

Abdominoplasty (abdominoplasty, liposuction);

Buttock plastic (gluteoplasty);

Arm plastic surgery (brachioplasty);

Plastic surgery of the inner surface of the lower leg and thigh (cruroplasty and femuroplasty);

Small and large labiaplasty (labioplasty);

Hymenoplasty (hymenoplasty);

Vagina plastic (vaginoplasty);

Penis (phalloplasty) and edge plastic surgery (preputioplasty);

Neck plastic surgery (plastismoplasty);

Skin tightening after weight loss (panniculectomy, torsoplasty);

Combinative plastic (two or more places);

Reconstructive plastic (massive external injuries).

One of the most popular aesthetic plastic surgeries is liposuction, which is performed in different areas depending on the instructions.

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